

КЛІНІЧНІ ТА АЛЕРГОЛОГІЧНІ РИСИ АЛЕРГІЧНОГО РИНИТУ У ДІТЕЙ ДОШКІЛЬНОГО ВІКУ

CLINICAL AND ALLERGOLOGICAL FEATURES OF ALLERGIC RHINITIS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Introduction. The issue of early detection of allergic rhinitis (AR) in children is extremely important, due to the need for early preventive detection of persons prone to bronchial asthma (BA), to achieve better control and prevention of severe disease and disability in children. Difficulties in diagnosing AR are due to its masking by the manifestations of acute respiratory viral diseases. Because respiratory viruses are inducers of acute rhinitis, often associated with AR, are provokers of subsequent exacerbations and subsequent formation of AR and often asthma. Timely allergy testing should increase the accuracy of diagnosis and guide the choice of treatment tactics.

The aim of this work was to study the clinical and allergic features of AR in young children by contacting an allergist.

Materials and methods: 30 preschool patients with AR who consulted an allergist at KDP NDSL "OKHMATDIT" were examined. Collection and analysis of clinical and anamnestic data, objective examination (anterior rhinoscopy, otoscopy), general clinical examinations, modern allergy diagnostics (determination of serum immunoglobulin E (IgE), skin tests with allergens, etc.). Statistical data processing -R program version i386 3.6.1., Excel.

Results: Among the surveyed children aged 2 to 6.5 years, boys predominated - 60%. All patients have a burdensome family history of allergies - mostly asthma in one or both parents. Early onset of the disease and the appearance of the first manifestations before the age of 1 year is observed in 20% of children. Complaints

were mostly sneezing and itchy nose - 77% of patients, sleep disorders - 70%, cough - 63%, rhinorrhea - 60% nasal congestion - 56%, dryness of the nasal mucosa - 23% - which significantly affected the quality of life of patients of this age group. Based on the data of the objective examination, the following frequency of clinical symptoms of AR is noted: difficulty in nasal breathing - 87% of patients, "allergic salute" - 63%, "allergic glow" - 77%, ocular symptoms - 17%, intoxication symptom - 67%; at anterior rhinoscopy a significant amount of white foamy secretion in the nasal passages -60%, swelling of the nasal sinuses with vasodilation-57%, symptom Voyachek -27%, runoff of light mucus on the posterior wall of the pharynx, causing spastic cough and slight hoarseness-57 %. The level of total serum immunoglobulin E (IgE) was significantly increased in all patients at a rate of up to 25 IU / ml, the average was 237.9 IU / ml. Skin testing for allergens was performed by the prick-test method, using standard techniques. Polyvalent sensitization to the most common allergens was detected in 30% of patients in this age group. Sensitization to *D. farinae*, *D. Pteronyssinus* (house dust mites) - was observed in 70% of subjects, to *Penicillium notatum*, *aspergillus fumigatus* (mold fungi) - 10%, to tree pollen (birch) - 23%, domestic animals - 20 % .

Conclusions: Thus, there is an early onset of allergic manifestations and high sensitization of young children to the most common allergens. This dictates the need for high vigilance regarding the active timely detection of allergic pathology in young children, especially in the presence of risk factors (burdensome family history of the patient, including). Skin allergen testing with prick test in young children is a truly affordable, safe, minimally invasive, rapid, sensitive and highly specific method of sensitization for the diagnosis of IgE-dependent reactions, which has a high degree of correlation with clinical manifestations.